

REVIEW OF THE REGULATORY FRAMEWORK RELEVANT TO THE PROTECTION OF WATER BODIES FROM EFFLUENTS INFLUENCED BY THE MINING INDUSTRY

Katerina Nikolova, Petia Genova, Rosen Ivanov, Polina Velichkova

University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”, Sofia

Corresponding author: k.nikolova@mgu.bg

ABSTRACT. This paper presents a targeted review and analysis of key regulatory documents related to the protection of water bodies impacted by the mining and processing industry. Bulgarian legislation is compared with the European normative framework, with focus on the parameters set out in a typical discharge permit for a mining site operator in Bulgaria. The main objective of the entire range of legislative norms in this area is long-term sustainable water management, a high level of protection of the aquatic environment, and setting out rules to halt deterioration in the status of EU water bodies and to achieve their good status.

Key words: mining industry, wastewater, legislation.

ПРЕГЛЕД НА НОРМАТИВНАТА БАЗА, ОТНАСЯЩА СЕ ЗА ОПАЗВАНЕ НА ВОДНИТЕ ТЕЛА ОТ ВОДИ, ПОВЛИЯНИ ОТ МИННАТА ИНДУСТРИЯ

Катерина Николова, Петя Генова, Росен Иванов, Полина Величкова

Минно-геоложки университет „Св. Иван Рилски“, 1700 София

РЕЗЮМЕ. В настоящата разработка е направен целеви преглед и анализ на основни нормативни документи, имащи отношение към опазване на водните тела, обект на натиск от миннодобивната и преработвателната промишленост. Съпоставено е българското законодателство с европейското, като основното внимание е фокусирано върху параметри, заложи в едно типично разрешително за заустване на оператор на минен обект в България. Основната цел на цялостната палитра от законодателни норми в тази сфера е дългосрочното устойчиво управление на водите, висока степен на защита на водната среда, постигане на добро състояние на всички водни тела при предотвратяване на допълнително влошаване на състоянието им.

Ключови думи: минна индустрия, отпадни води, законодателство.

Introduction

Given the fundamental importance of environmental legislation for ensuring sustainable development, mining companies should comply with the environmental restrictions set, regardless of any difficulties although our civilisation is now highly vulnerable to supply risks concerning specific mineral raw materials (Falck and Correia, 2023). The raw materials are essential to secure the future generations in respect of climate and energy challenges (Reichl and Schatz, 2023).

As Correia et al. (2024) stated, the European energy transition has to be faced towards human rights, social sustainability, and ecological standards. Resource extraction within the EU is fully aligned with those principles, as it occurs under more stringent regulations than in most other countries and utilises shorter supply lines. Another issue is the necessary support for stakeholders in building relationships based on responsibility, adaptivity, respect of local political and authority structures and customs (Tost et al., 2024). The sector has to make crucial decisions that would define the future goals set in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the Paris Agreement (UN TransfEISusDev, 2021). The mineral and raw materials industry is important for Bulgaria and has been one of the best developing sectors in recent years. Regarding labour productivity, this sector is closest to the EU average and significantly exceeds the average productivity for other sectors. Bulgaria is one of the countries in the European Union that, along with Germany, Austria, Poland, the Czech Republic, Romania, Sweden, and others, has long-standing traditions and experience in the development of the mineral and raw materials industry. More than 300 companies and organisations in the field of exploration, extraction, and processing of underground resources are working nowadays, with about 25 000 people

directly working in the sector, with labour productivity which is 2.5 times higher than the average for the industrial sector, and at about 5% of the country's gross domestic product.

The national legislative frame is based on good practices both in the EU and in Bulgaria, which should be implemented and continuously improved to achieve sustainable development of the mining industry (EU Green Deal, 2019; CEAP, 2020). The environmental legislation in Bulgaria regulates two main types of public relations: environmental protection from pollution (the qualitative dimension of the environment) and rational use of natural resources (quantitative dimension). Some of the most viral aspects of the strategy of sustainable development of the branch both in Europe and in Bulgaria are directly focused on the environmental protection: environmental management, biodiversity protection, energy and climate protection, waste management, emissions mitigation.

Water treatment in the mining industry is becoming increasingly critical. Environmental regulations and water scarcity require operators to find innovative, practical solutions for sustainable water management. A treatment plan must be created that is safe for the environment and for operations when handling mine water. Water from mining and ore processing often contains significant amounts of dissolved and undissolved contaminants, some of which are toxic. The presence of water in the mine can lead to fluctuations in the water table or overflows in underground and open-pit mines, so it must be discharged.

Preparing the present study on the normative base for the treatment of wastewater influenced by mining and extractive industry, the following were taken into consideration: regulations on the management of waste from the mining and processing industry and the water quality, as well as the main regulatory framework affecting the mining industry. The focus is set on Bulgarian and European key regulatory documents related to

the protection of water bodies impacted by the mining and processing industry, regarding typical indicators for a mining effluent: pH, sulphates, electrical conductivity, heavy metals, etc.

Basis of Bulgarian national legislation on the protection of water and water bodies affected by mining industry

The state environmental policy is based on a set of ideas, principles, and practical approaches to solve the environmental problems of the society, united in different legal acts, namely complexity in the legal regulation of the environment; scientific substantiation of management decisions; prevention through environmental protection; combination of national legislation with the European and International legislation; the “polluter pays” principle; public participation in environmental management.

Preparing the present feasibility study on normative acceptable options for the treatment of the extractive waste influenced waters (EWIW) before discharge, regulations on the management of waste from the mining and processing industry and the water quality are taken into consideration. Some of the most important of them are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. BG national policy

ACTS
Environment Protection Act
Water Act
Subsurface Resources Act
REGULATIONS
Regulation on the Management of Mining Waste, 2016
Regulation 10 /2001 on Issuing Permits for Waste Water Discharge into Water Bodies and Setting Individual Emission Limit Values for Point Sources of Pollution
Regulation H-4/2012 for characterization of surface waters
Regulation on Standards for Environmental Quality for Priority Substances and Certain Other Pollutants, 2010
Regulation 6/2000 on the Limit Values for Admissible Contents of Dangerous and Harmful Substances in the Waste Water Discharged in the Water Bodies
OTHERS
Methodology for BAT determination, 2012
National Strategy for the Development of the Mining Industry, 2015

National Strategy for the Development of the Mining Industry

The strategy strives for the sustainable development of the mining industry by ensuring a balanced economic, social, and ecologically responsible approach to exploration, extraction, and processing of underground natural resources in the Republic of Bulgaria. The realization of the general and specific strategic objectives aims at prerequisites and legal guarantees for the sustainable development of the mining industry in Bulgaria in accordance with the European Initiative for raw materials and the implementation of a unified and clear state policy on the underground natural resources of the country. To achieve this, it is intended to use good practices, both in the EU and in Bulgaria, which can and should be continuously implemented and improved to achieve sustainable development of the mining industry.

Environmental Protection Act (EPA)

According to Art. 3 of EPA, the protection of the environment is based on a number of principles. In particular, considering the importance of the treatment of effluents before their discharge, the following are of a primary significance:

- prevention and reduction of the risk for human health;
- the advantage of preventing pollution from the subsequent elimination of the damage it causes;
- the polluter pays for the caused damages;
- prevention from pollution and damage of clean areas and other adverse impacts on them;
- integration of environmental policy into sectoral and regional policies for the development of the economy and social relations.

Water Act (WA)

The WA regulates the ownership and management of the waters on the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria as a common national inseparable natural resource and the ownership of the water-saving systems and facilities. The purpose of the act is to:

- ensure an integrated water management in the interest of society,
- protect the health of the population,
- to create conditions for ensuring sufficient and good quality of surface and groundwater for sustainable, balanced, and legitimate water use, reducing water pollution,
- protect surface and groundwater and Black Sea waters, ceasing pollution of the marine environment with natural or synthetic substances;
- reduce discharges, emissions, and release of priority substances;
- discontinue discharges, emissions, and release of priority hazardous substances;
- prevent or reduce harmful effects on human life and health, the environment, cultural heritage, and economic activity, related to the adverse impacts of water.

Chapter 8 of the WA regulates water and water bodies issues based on the principle that all waters and water bodies are protected from exhaustion, pollution, damage, in order to:

- maintain the necessary quantity and quality of water and a healthy environment,
- conserve ecosystems,
- preserve the landscape,
- prevent economic damages, including:
 - achieving good chemical and ecological status of surface water,
 - achieving good quantitative and chemical status of groundwater,
 - reducing the need for water treatment before use,
 - ensuring the development of aquatic ecosystems and associated terrestrial ecosystems.

Regulation on Standards for Environmental Quality for Priority Substances and Certain Other Pollutants

This document establishes environmental quality standards (EQS) for priority substances and certain other pollutants in order to achieve good chemical status of surface waters in accordance with the provisions and objectives of Chapter 10, Section III, of the Water Act. Such substances, typical for mining activities, are lead, nickel, mercury and cadmium.

Basis of the European legislation on the protection of waters and water bodies from water affected by the mining industry

Analysing the EU legal documents, it must first be said that the Environment, and Mining and Processing sectoral policies follow the primacy of the European Union's legislative acts and other principles, i.e. they follow the structure of *Acquis Communautaire*.

Table 2. EU policy

DIRECTIVES	
ID	Title
2006/21/EC	Directive on the management of waste from extractive industries
2010/75/EU	Directive on industrial emissions (integrated pollution prevention and control)
2000/60/EC	Directive establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy (EU Water Framework Directive)
2006/118/EC	Directive on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration
2014/80/EU	Directive amending Annex II to Directive 2006/118/EC on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration
2008/105/EC	Directive 2008/105/EC setting environmental quality standards in the field of water policy
2013/39/EU	Directive amending Directives 2000/60/EC and 2008/105/EC as regards priority substances in the field of water policy
2014/52/EU	Directive on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment (EIA)
2002/49/EC	Directive relating to the assessment and management of environmental noise
2012/18/EU	Directive on the control of major-accident hazards involving dangerous substances
2003/4/EC	Directive on public access to environmental information
2003/35/EC	Directive providing for public participation in respect of the drawing up of certain plans and programmes relating to the environment
EC EXTRA DOCUMENTS RELATED TO WASTE MANAGEMENT AND MINE CLOSURE	
Type	Title
Resolution	EP resolution of 5 May 2010 on a general ban on the use of cyanide mining technologies in the European Union
Strategy	Mediterranean Action Plan (MAP)
Guidance Note	Preparing a Waste Management Plan
	Safety guidelines and good practices for tailings management facilities, UNECE, 2014
BREF	Best Available Techniques Reference Document for the Management of Waste from Extractive Industries (MWEI BREF), in accordance with Directive 2006/21/EC, 2018
	Best Available Techniques for the Management of Tailings and Waste Rock in Mining Activities (MTWR BREF)

Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy (WFD)

The environmental objectives are set out in Article 4 of the Water Framework Directive. The aim is a long-term sustainable water management, based on a high level of protection of the aquatic environment. Article 4 (1) defines the overall WFD objective to be achieved for all surface and groundwater bodies, achieving good status until 2015 and introducing the principle of preventing further deterioration. The main environmental objectives of the Directive are various and include the following elements, according to Article 4 (1) of the WFD:

- preventing deterioration of surface and groundwater,
- protecting, improving and repairing all water bodies, achieving good status by 2015, i.e. (or potentially) good ecological status as well as good chemical status of surface water and good chemical and quantitative status of groundwater,
- gradual reduction of pollution with certain substances and stepwise cease of the discharge of priority hazardous substances in surface water,
- prevention and limitation of the introduction of pollutants into groundwater,
- suspension of any significant upward trends in groundwater pollution,
- achievement of standards and targets for protected areas defined in Community legislation.

Directive 2008/105/EC setting environmental quality standards in the field of water policy

It sets out environmental quality standards (EQSs) concerning the presence in surface water of certain substances or groups of substances identified as priority pollutants because of the significant risk they pose to or via the aquatic environment. These standards are in line with the strategy and objectives of the EU Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC). These substances include the metals cadmium, lead, mercury and nickel, and their compounds. The limits on the concentration of the priority substances and 8 other pollutants in water (or biota) are given, i.e. thresholds which must not be exceeded if a good chemical status is to be met. There are 2 types of water standard:

- A threshold for the average concentration of the substance concerned, calculated from measurements over a 1-year period. The purpose of this standard is to ensure protection against long-term exposure to pollutants in the aquatic environment;
- A maximum allowable concentration of the substance concerned, i.e. the maximum for any single measurement. The purpose of this standard is to ensure protection against short-term exposure, i.e. pollution peaks.

EU countries must ensure compliance with the EQSs. They must also take measures to ensure that the concentrations of substances that tend to accumulate in sediment and/or biota do not increase significantly. For each river basin district, EU countries must set up an inventory of emissions, discharges, and losses of all substances listed in Part A of Annex I to the directive.

Directive 2006/21/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 March 2006 on the management of waste from extractive industries (MWEI DIRECTIVE)

As stated in Directive 2006/21/EC, a follow-up to recent mining accidents sets out as one of its priority actions an

initiative to regulate the management of waste from the extractive industries. This action is designed to complement initiatives pursuant to Directive 2003/105/EC on the control of major-accident hazards involving dangerous substances, as well as the production of a best available technique document covering the management of waste rock and tailings from mining activities.

Best Available Techniques

In order to define Best Available Techniques (BAT) and the BAT-associated environmental performance at EU level, the Commission organises an exchange of information with experts from Member States, industry and environmental organisations. This process results in BAT Reference Documents (BREFs), as the BAT conclusions contained are adopted by the Commission as Implementing Decisions.

Best Available Techniques Reference Document for the Management of Waste from Extractive Industries (MWEI BREF)

Technologies for the treatment of wastewater influenced by the mining industry as set in the BAT Reference Document for the Management of Waste from extractive industries, MWEI BREF, is a review of the Reference Document for Management of Tailings and Waste-Rock in Mining Activities (MTWR BREF). The reviewed document presents up-dated data and information on the management of waste from extractive industries, including information on BAT, associated monitoring, and developments in them. Member States shall ensure that operators responsible for the management of extractive waste take all measures necessary to prevent or reduce as far as possible any adverse effects on the environment and human health brought about as a result of the management of extractive waste. These measures shall be based, *inter alia*, on the best available techniques without prescribing the use of any technique or specific technology, but taking into account the technical characteristics of the waste facility, its geographical location, and the local environmental conditions.

The BAT implementation is fully overlapped with the European policy to circular approach as extractive wastes are to be re-mined. (Blengini et al., 2019; Garbarino et al., 2020)

According to MWEI BREF, the strategies for management of the extractive waste influenced waters (EWIW) can be divided in dependence to the two main streams:

- unrecovered water (seepage): prevention or reduction of seepage from non-inert extractive waste deposition areas;
- recovered water (drained water and free water to be re-used, recycled or discharged): this may represent important volumes in some cases.

EWIW may be re-used or recycled (after treatment) for the mineral processing or other extraction activities. The EWIW stemming from the EWFs, which cannot or will not be further used, is usually discharged by operators, often after treatment, in rivers or seawater bodies in most cases, and/or in lakes in some cases.

The most common environmental impacts of emissions to water are acidification of rivers, emissions of suspended particles, and emissions of dissolved substances, such as salts and metals. In order to prevent and control emissions, but also as a valuable source of water to be recycled and re-used, the management of EWIW is of the utmost importance in any

mineral resources extraction project since water plays a key role in most extraction processes.

The water at an extractive site can be divided into two main types of water streams:

- the water which was not in contact with the extractive waste at any stage of the process, e.g. water run-off;
- the EWIW which was in contact with the extractive waste at some stage of the process, e.g. water from the mineral processing, reclaimed water from the EWF, drainage water.

Operators usually try to avoid the contact of water run-off with the mineral resources or extractive waste. Different techniques, such as diversion channels and waste covers, are used to avoid contact and prevent water contamination. The EWIW is usually collected and treated. After treatment, water can be re-used, e.g. in the mineral processing. Only the excess water which is not needed, or which can affect the stability of the EWFs, is discharged as a surplus. The treatment of water prior to discharge aims to prevent and control any negative environmental impacts. In some cases, e.g. for smaller EWIW volumes, the treatment of water may be carried out in specialised water treatment facilities (off site). However, for larger volumes of EWIW, the treatment is carried out on site.

In general, the different techniques used for the management of EWIW can be divided into two categories: active techniques, i.e. requiring energy input, and passive techniques, i.e. not requiring energy input. Active techniques will also require more maintenance than passive techniques. Moreover, the different treatment techniques can be grouped into three broad categories, according to the intended purpose: the separation of phases, the removal of dissolved substances, and the neutralisation of EWIW. For each of these categories, operators reported the implementation of several techniques.

Basically, the MWEI BREF does not provide legal interpretation, nor should it be used to such purpose. It aims to provide technical information related to BAT referring to a broad range of materials and processes. The BAT Conclusions should therefore be seen as a reference aiming at:

- providing extractive industries, competent authorities, and other relevant stakeholders with up-to-date information and data on the management of extractive waste;
- supporting decision makers by providing a list of identified BAT to prevent or reduce as far as possible any adverse effects on the environment and human health brought about as a result of the management of extractive waste, duly taking into account that the techniques listed and described are neither prescriptive nor exhaustive and that other techniques may be used that ensure at least an equivalent level of environmental protection.

There are two distinct groups of BAT, generic and risk-specific. Generic BAT focus on corporate management; information and data management (including the site-specific information and the evaluation of environmental risks and impacts); and waste hierarchy. Risk-specific BAT comprise BAT identified to prevent or reduce as far as possible specific risks that are identified by a proper Environmental Risk and Impact Evaluation, duly considering the relevant site-specific information. In order to prevent or minimise surface water status deterioration, BAT is to use one or a combination of techniques, appropriately pre-selected and based on the abated pollutants or targeted parameters, applicability of the respective technique, and the financial, administrative, and technical capacity of the operator. All the variants (Tables 3, 4 and 5) are based on the results of a proper Environmental Risk and Impact Evaluation,

as different techniques are relevant to different groups of pollutants to be abated.

Removal of suspended solids / suspended liquid particles

In order to reduce the level of suspended solids (TSS) or (SL) liquid particles in the EWIW, operators reported implementing one or a combination of the following techniques (Table 3):

- gravity separation: based on the principle of natural gravity sedimentation;
- clarification in tanks: based on the gravity settling principle enhanced by a mechanical system to remove solids being deposited by sedimentation;
- coagulation and flocculation: based on the use of chemicals to enhance sedimentation;
- air flotation: based on the capturing of solid particles in froth;
- media filtration: based on the size exclusion of particles and/or capture of particles;
- membrane filtration: based on size exclusion (pore size).

Some of the applicability cases may be restricted by location and land availability (BAT 45 a), by the properties of the particles, naturally or by means of flotation reagents, to attach to air bubbles (BAT 45 d), or by a non-constant inflow quality and/or high TSS content (BAT 45 g). Media and membrane filtration are particularly relevant for non-inert EWIW (BAT 45 e and f), as hydrocycloning could be used for treatment of extractive waste from mineral processing to be deposited into ponds (BAT 45 g).

Table 3. Removal of suspended solids/suspended liquid particles

Technique - BAT 45	Targeted parameters
a) Gravity separation in settling ponds	TSS, SL such as oil and grease
b) Clarification in tanks	TSS, SL such as oil and grease
c) Coagulation and flocculation	TSS, SL such as oil and grease, colloids
d) Air flotation	TSS, SL such as oil and grease, emulsions, COD
e) Media filtration	TSS
f) Membrane filtration for suspended particles	TSS, SL such as oil and grease, colloids
g) Hydrocycloning	TSS

Removal of dissolved substances

For the reduction of the level of dissolved substances in the EWIW (Table 4), operators reported implementing one or a combination of the following techniques based on the following:

• *The oxidation and/or aeration principle:*

- Aeration of the water stream and/or addition of oxidants in order to promote the oxidation and precipitation of dissolved substances, mainly dissolved metals.

- Active aerobic biological oxidation or implementation of passive aerobic wetlands where the biological activity of microorganisms promotes the oxidation and precipitation of dissolved substances.

• *The reduction principle:*

- Anaerobic wetlands or anoxic Biochemical Reactors (BCRs) can be used to promote the reduction and precipitation of dissolved substances.

• *The neutralisation/precipitation principle:*

- Hydroxide and carbonate precipitation is implemented to precipitate dissolved metals into a hydroxide or carbonate complex. This is performed by adding alkaline reagents to the EWIW, which leads to a pH rise and the precipitation of dissolved metals.

- Sulphide precipitation is implemented to precipitate dissolved metals into a sulphide complex by adding sulphide reagents to the EWIW, which leads to the precipitation of dissolved metals.

• *The adsorption principle:*

- Adsorption of dissolved substances on inorganic or organic media, based on the surface properties of the media and the liquid-solid interactions, can be used to remove the dissolved substances, e.g. active carbon adsorption or ion exchange.

• *The size exclusion principle:*

- Nanofiltration and reverse osmosis.

It has to be pointed that BAT 46 a is not applicable as a stand-alone technique, but in combination with other techniques such as precipitation, solid/liquid control, and pH adjustment. The applicability of *active aerobic biological oxidation* may be restricted in the case of high levels of BOD or COD, oil or salts which would prevent the microbial oxidation.

Table 4. Removal of dissolved substances

Technique - BAT 46	Targeted parameters
a) Aeration and active chemical oxidation	Fe ²⁺ , Mn ²⁺
b) Active aerobic biological oxidation	Oil/grease, nitrogen, cyanates, COD, BOD, metals
c) Aerobic wetlands	TDS, TSS, BOD, metals
d) Anaerobic wetlands	Acidity, dissolved metals and metalloids, sulphates
e) BCRs	Acidity, dissolved metals and metalloids, sulphates
f) Hydroxide and carbonate precipitation	Dissolved metals
g) Sulphide precipitation	Dissolved metals and metalloids
h) Coprecipitation with chloride or sulphate metal salts	As, P, Se, 226Ra
i) Adsorption	Dissolved metals, organic carbon, BTEX, oil, and grease
j) Ion exchange	Ca, Mn, Ba, Sr, Ra, nitrates, fluorides, arsenates, chromates, U complexes, B, and HMs
k) Nanofiltration	Multivalent ions
l) Reverse osmosis	Dissolved metals, salts, macromolecules

The *aerobic and anaerobic wetlands* (BAT 46 c and d) could be used as polishing technique regarding the various limitations for their use:

- high acidity load,
- high levels of salts which would prevent event proper microbial oxidation,
- high dissolved oxygen content,
- high water flow,
- low land availability,
- decreasing effectiveness over time,
- high temperature and flow fluctuations,

- adverse local climatic conditions,
- sensitivity to high throughput excursions.

They are not applicable as a stand-alone technique. Also, maintenance could be required, so their operation is often hard. BCRs are applicable to sites with little available space and very strict emission limits. Compared to other sulfate reduction methods (e.g. reactive barriers, bioreactors), special equipment and maintenance activities are needed. They are not applicable with high levels of salts that would prevent proper microbial oxidation.

Hydroxide and carbonate precipitation (BAT 46 f) is not suitable for the removal of chromium, selenium and uranium. Its applicability may be restricted in the presence of chelates, such as ammonia, and metal-complexing agents, such as cyanides. *Sulphide precipitation* (BAT 46 g) could be used only in combination with other techniques, such as solid/liquid separation, and is suitable for valuable metals recovery from the EWIW stream. The feasibility of *coprecipitation* may be restricted in the case of sensitiveness to higher variations in EWIW quality (BAT 46 h), while that of the *adsorption* - in the case of high levels of salts which would prevent proper adsorption (BAT 46 i). The *ion exchange*, *nanofiltration*, and *reverse osmosis* (BAT 46 j, k and l) are very sensitive to peak concentrations and extreme conditions – pH variations, temperature alterations, high levels of salts which would prevent proper ion exchange, nanofiltration or reverse osmosis. Usually, they are applied as a polishing step.

Finally, in order to adjust the pH of EWIW, implementing one or a combination of the following techniques is required:

- active neutralisation based on the addition of basic or alkaline reagents;
- passive treatment based on the passive dissolution of alkaline reagents:
 - Oxic Limestone Drains (OLDs), Open Limestone Channels (OLCs);
 - Anoxic Limestone Drains (ALDs);
 - Successive Alkalinity-Producing Systems (SAPS).

Table 5. Neutralisation of EWIW prior to discharge

Technique - BAT 47	Targeted parameters
a) Active neutralization	pH, acidity, alkalinity
b) OLDs/OLCs	Acidity, Mn, Al, Fe, Cu, Pb, etc.
c) ALDs	Acidity
d) SAPS	Acidity, Al, Cu, Fe, Mn, Zn
e) Anaerobic wetlands	As per BAT 46 d

The techniques for neutralisation before discharge (BAT 47 a - e) (Table 5) have also some limitations – they are not applicable to treat high levels of metal content and/or acidity, high concentration of Fe, Al, high acidity, high flow rate, higher levels of DO or low pH. Therefore, the techniques may be particularly suitable as a polishing technique, during the operational phase, or for the treatment of low-load EWIW from sites in the closure or after closure phase, and are not sufficient as a stand-alone technique. Their applicability may be restricted by land availability and site topography.

Conclusions

The specifics of the extraction and processing of mineral resources lead to an enormous impact on water bodies, and are therefore subject to regulation by environmental legislation. In

order to minimise the negative impacts of mining on the environment, a thorough verification (independent quality assessment) of mining projects is necessary. The national legislative frame is based on good practices both in the EU and in Bulgaria, which should be implemented and continuously improved to achieve sustainable development of the mining industry.

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